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Effect of Uv Radiation on DNA and Nucleohistone— A Preliminary Study†

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Manuscript received 6 June 1986, revised 1 December 1986,
accepted 9 March 1987

THE effect of uv radiation on nucleohistone (DNH) is important as it is a constituent of chromosome. The constituent moieties of nucleohistone that are sensitive to uv radiation are thymine¹, cytosine² and DNA³. Deoxyribose is not expected to undergo any significant photochemical reactions at the experimental wavelength (*i.e.* 254 nm)⁴. The purpose of this study is to find the difference in the degree of denaturation between DNA and nucleohistone and any reason for the same.

Experimental

Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) (Lot No. D 1501) and nucleohistone (DNH) (Lot No. 4943) obtained from Sigma and Calbiochem, respectively, were dissolved in ECA (10^{-3} M EDTA, 10^{-3} M sodium cacodylate, pH 8.0) at a concentration of 30 μ g ml⁻¹. The native compounds as obtained do not get denatured on standing if cacodylic acid is present in the solution⁵. The solutions were kept in petri dishes of surface area 12.25 cm², the solution thickness being 0.82 cm. The temperature of irradiation was kept at a reported⁶ value of about 4° and there was no notable change of temperature

due to uv irradiation. The exposure dose at a fixed distance of 11.18 cm was 900×10^8 erg mm⁻².

The uv lamp (Arthur Thomas, U.K.) used emitted characteristic radiation of λ_{max} 254 and 365 nm; in the present study 254 nm radiation was used. Arrangements for variation of exposure dose, swirling of solution during irradiation, avoidance of back scattered radiation and ordinary light were made.

Results and Discussion

From Fig. 1 it is evident that the absorption maximum is at 258 nm for unirradiated DNA. The optical absorbance values, with standard deviations for unirradiated DNA at 230, 240, 250 and 260 nm are 0.180 ± 0.02 , 0.230 ± 0.01 , 0.335 ± 0.02 and 0.370 ± 0.02 , respectively. That for irradiated DNA at these wavelengths are respectively 0.235 ± 0.01 , 0.320 ± 0.01 , 0.485 ± 0.02 and 0.550 ± 0.01 . The average absorbance for these wavelengths for unirradiated DNA is 0.39. The average percentage hyperchromicity is 31.37%. It signifies that denaturation of the biopolymer has taken place. The structure is disorganised by uv radiation before there is any extensive photochemical degradation of the bases⁷. As the irradiation has not been done in a nitrogen atmosphere, the possibility of main chain scission in the DNA molecule in presence of oxygen can not be ruled out⁸. The chromophoric groups responsible for absorption in the uv spectral range studied are available more in solution when main chain scission takes place. Hence, the hyperchromicity is obtained at all the wavelengths.

Fig. 1. Uv absorption spectra of unirradiated and uv irradiated DNA; concn. of DNA = 30 μ g ml⁻¹, dose of uv irradiation = 900 erg mm⁻²: (O) unirradiated DNA, and (●) uv irradiated DNA.

†Presented in part at the 53rd Annual Meeting of the Society of Biological Chemists, 1984, Delhi.

From Fig. 2 it is observed that compared to unirradiated DNH there is hyperchromicity in uv irradiated solution. The absorbance values for unirradiated DNH at the same wavelengths as that

Fig. 2. Uv absorption spectra of unirradiated and uv irradiated DNH; concn. of DNH = $30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, dose of uv irradiation = 900 erg mm^{-2} : (O) unirradiated DNH, and (●) uv irradiated DNH.

of DNA are 0.170 ± 0.03 , 0.190 ± 0.02 , 0.250 ± 0.02 and 0.280 ± 0.02 , hence the average value being 0.22. For irradiated DNH at the same wavelengths the absorbance values are 0.290 ± 0.04 , 0.310 ± 0.04 , 0.370 ± 0.05 and 0.390 ± 0.05 , the average value being 0.34. The average percentage hyperchromicity is 15.57%. So for the same concentration and dose, the average percentage hyperchromicity value for DNH is half than that of DNA. It has been reported⁹ that the change produced in DNA when irradiated as a nucleoprotein complex inside cells are qualitatively and quantitatively different from those that are produced when pure DNA is treated. In the present case, though it is not cellular nucleoprotein, the protein coat on DNA definitely protects it from uv radiation damage¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

Guidance and encouragement given by Dr. A. Ghose, Head, Radiation Biology Department and Maj. Gen. N. Lakshminpathi, V.S.M., Director is gratefully acknowledged.

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Synthesis of New Flavone

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Manuscript received 23 July 1985, revised 4 June 1986, accepted 9 March 1987

THE isolation and characterisation of 5-*O*-methylacacetin (1) from the heartwood of *Adina cordifolia* has been reported previously by Srivastava¹. The present communication reports the synthesis² of 1 and its 7-*O*-methyl derivative (2). This synthesis of 1 further supports its structure.

Condensation of 4-*O*-benzyl-2-*O*-methylphloroacetophenone (3) and 2,4-di-*O*-methylphloroacetophenone with anisaldehyde in alkali yielded the corresponding chalcones 4 and 5, respectively, which on SeO_2 treatment afforded 7-*O*-benzyl-5-*O*-methylacacetin (6) and 5,7-di-*O*-methylacacetin (7), respectively. The acacetin (6) on debenzoylation gave a product which was identical to the natural flavone (1). The required phloroacetophenone methyl ethers were prepared by methylation of phloroacetophenone³, while anisaldehyde was prepared by formylation of anisole^{4,5}.

Experimental

Methyl ethers of phloroacetophenone: A mixture of phloroacetophenone (4 g), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (10 g), Me_2SO_4 (3 ml) and dry Me_2CO (100 ml) was refluxed for 5 h and worked up. The product was separated by column chromatography over silica gel into 2,4-di-*O*-methyl- (m.p. $80-1^\circ$, 1.50 g), 4-*O*-methyl- (m.p. $139-40^\circ$, 800 mg) and 2-*O*-methylphloroacetophenones (m.p. $204-5^\circ$, 800 mg).

Synthesis of 1: 2-*O*-Methylphloroacetophenone (500 mg) was dissolved in dry Me_2CO (50 ml) and refluxed with benzyl chloride (4 ml) in the presence of K_2CO_3 (2 g) for 3 h⁶. Usual work-up and crystallisation from Me_2CO -EtOAc mixture yielded 3 (415 mg), m.p. $130-32^\circ$.

A mixture of 3 (400 mg) and anisaldehyde (440 mg) in EtOH (15 ml) containing aqueous NaOH